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**MORPHO-SYNTACTIC ANALYSIS OF SOLECISMS IN MEMORANDA FROM THE
REGISTRY DEPARTMENT OF THE FEDERAL COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
(SPECIAL), OYO**

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Abstract

There is a growing concern about the decline in the quality of English use in Nigeria. Some scholars have investigated the situation at various levels of linguistic analysis in different domains, including tertiary institutions. However, there is a dearth of such exploration regarding official documents from the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. It is against the backdrop of this research gap that this paper focuses on morpho-syntactic solecisms in memoranda issued by the Registry Department of the institution with the objectives of identifying, analysing and categorising them. The purposive sampling technique was used to select thirty (30) representative internal memos produced between 2021 and 2023 that were studied. Anchored in Error Analysis, the study identified two hundred and six (206) solecisms, which were grouped in twelve (12) error taxonomies. Findings show that punctuation errors with fifty-three (53, 25%) instances were the most dominant, while fragment/collocational/formulaic error (1, 0.5%) was the least frequent. Additionally, findings reveal that, notwithstanding their error categories, frequencies, and percentages, these errors are linguistically significant because they highlight the poor quality of English observed in memos from the institution in question.

Keywords: Morpho-Syntactic, Solecisms, Memoranda, Registry Department, College of Education.

Introduction

The paper explores the prevalent grammatical inaccuracies within the official documents produced by staff of the Registry Department of a Nigerian tertiary educational institution, the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. The study investigates and explicates morpho-syntactic errors in official writings, particularly memoranda of the institution.

Errors, often termed solecisms, encompass deviations in both morphological (word formation) and syntactic (sentence structure) aspects of the English language. Improper usage of English as a second language in structures reflects both grammatical and interference problems. Thus, verb-tense errors, subject-verb agreement errors, inappropriate use of genitive and punctuation marks, word order errors, incorrect pluralisation, and article issues are functions of morpho-syntactic solecisms.

In Nigeria, English serves as the official language and the principal medium of instruction across educational tiers. English plays a dominant role, not only in education but also in legislation, media, administration, and inter-ethnic communication. The pervasive functions of English in Nigeria make it almost a *sine qua non* in the country's sociolinguistic and educational contexts. According to Bamgbose (2000), English in Nigeria functions not only as a *lingua franca* but also as the language of prestige and opportunity, thereby placing a critical demand on tertiary education institutions to use English accurately and appropriately, especially in written official documents that define policy and procedure.

Effective communication in tertiary education institutions is significant for ensuring clarity, smooth administration, and establishing close rapport among staff, students and external stakeholders. This paper focuses on the Registry Department because, according to Okebukola (2017), it is the "heart" of the entire system of administration in any tertiary educational institution.

Eyisi (2003) highlights that ineffective communication, especially in written form, can hamper decision-making, lead to misunderstandings, and affect the institution's image. She observes that grammatically flawed communication undermines the credibility of administrative messages and contributes to inefficiency in institutional operations. In a similar vein, Akere (2009) agrees that the ability to convey ideas precisely and professionally in written form is a core component of effective administration and academic culture in educational institutions. However, administrative documents that are fraught with morpho-syntactic solecisms reflect a lacuna in communicative competence and can distort information and reduce the effectiveness of institutional correspondence. Adebijaja (2004) avers that solecisms in official writings compromise the standard expected of academic institutions, and such errors often stem from inadequate mastery of English grammar, linguistic interference and ineffective pedagogical grounding. It is within this context that official writings from educational institutions exhibit morpho-syntactic deviations from the Standard British English (SBE), which is the norm.

Morpho-syntactic accuracy, which reflects correct usage of grammatical forms and sentence structures, is critical in formal writing, especially within educational institutions. Ekundayo (2013) explains that morpho-syntactic solecisms are not merely slips but a reflection of deeper issues of lack of competence and the influence of the first language. He introduced the concept of "intraference", describing how even educated users of English in Nigeria often generate incorrect forms due to overgeneralization.

It is conclusive, therefore, to aver that there is an inextricable interconnectedness of language competence and educational efficiency. Ensuring morpho-syntactic accuracy in official writings is a matter of functional necessity that engenders credibility, clarity and professionalism in tertiary education institutions. It is against this backdrop that this study focuses on the analysis of morpho-syntactic solecisms in the administrative writings of a Nigerian College of Education.

Statement of the Problem

English is the official language and the principal language of instruction and communication across all levels of education in Nigeria. Thus, effective communication within educational institutions is critical for clarity, efficiency and professionalism. Nevertheless, the presence of solecisms in word formation and sentence structure can significantly impede official correspondence channels such as memoranda, circulars, and reports, which often serve as the primary means of communication. If these documents are riddled with grammatical inconsistencies, they not only undermine institutional credibility and image but also reflect broader issues in staff language proficiency. Despite the crucial significance of written communication in administrative contexts, scholarly attention to the linguistic quality of such documents in Nigerian colleges of education remains limited. This oversight is problematic, as official writings, often couched by registry department staff, play a key role in decision-making, policy implementation and operations of colleges of education.

Admittedly, there are revealing and exciting studies that have been done on errors made by Nigerian users of English. Most of these extant works such as Fakoya (2015) Obiegbu (2018), Balogun (2020), Odebunmi (2020) and Obi, Molta & Timayi (2024), focus on errors in students and lecturers' spoken and written English, leaving a gap in the language use of administrative staff of tertiary institutions.

Fakoya (2015) examines the sources and causes of errors in the English of Nigerians and establishes that those errors result from the interference of autochthonous languages, general linguistic, psychological, and pedagogical factors, as well as the influence of socio-cultural and communicative pressures. Focusing on English usage of educated Nigerians (younger and older), Obiegbu (2018) found various types of syntactic errors they commit, which impinge on their communication effectiveness. Balogun (2020) studies modality errors in the written scripts

of selected secondary school students. Her findings reveal inappropriate use of modalities to express formality and politeness and that poor mastery of English grammatical rules is a major cause of the modality errors among the students. In his study on the decline in the quality of written and spoken English in Nigeria, Odebunmi (2020) establishes that the quality of English, particularly among university lecturers and students, has declined considerably, hampering individual and corporate communication output and job performance. Obi, Molta & Timayi (2024) studied errors in the written English of tertiary institution students. Their findings highlight that most students commit grammatical errors in subject-verb agreement, spelling, capitalisation, incorrect verb forms and incorrect word order.

From the foregoing, it is evident that scholars have not paid much attention to error analysis in official writings of the official writings of tertiary institutions in Nigeria, particularly in colleges of education. It is against this backdrop that the paper investigates morpho-syntactic solecisms in the memoranda produced by the Registry Department of the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, Nigeria. Filling this gap can enhance effective communication through memoranda in the Registry Department of the institution.

Aim and Objectives

This paper investigates morpho-syntactic solecisms in internal memoranda of the Registry Department of the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the paper are to:

- i. identify the morpho-syntactic solecisms in the memoranda of the Registry Department of the institution being studied;
- ii. explore the types of morpho-syntactic solecisms in the memoranda of the Registry Department of the College being studied; and

- iii. establish the frequency and percentage of the error types.

Literature Review

The English language is the officially prescribed language of governance in Nigeria; hence, all official documents, whether in soft copy or hard copy, are expected to be communicated first in English. The importance of good written communication cannot be overstated because it is the driver of effective administration of any organisation or institution.

Hornby (2020) defines communication as the activity or process of expressing ideas and feelings or of giving people information. In crafting any information, Wordy (2023) advises that when communicating in writing, it is essential to remember some basic communication guidelines to ensure that the information needed is provided in an appropriate manner because unclear, vague communication or communicating only some of the information can lead to misunderstandings. Manafa (2018) is of the view that a problem in any of the elements in the process of communication, namely the sender, message, channel, and receiver can lead to communication ineffectiveness. Thus, the use of correct English grammar, spelling and punctuation, as well as the use of proper style for formal writing, is critical to effective communication.

In the context of official documentation in the College of Education, formal institutional British writing is the recommended norm. It helps to establish credibility, ensures clear communication, and maintains professionalism, reflecting the institution's commitment to high standards and effective internal and external communication. According to Conrad, Biber, and Leech (2002), formal writing within institutions exhibits a high degree of grammatical accuracy which contributes to an objective and official tone.

Nordquist (2019) defines solecism as an offence against the rules of grammar by the use of words in wrong construction. He further explains the term as any word or expression that does

not conform to the established usage of writing or speaking. Therefore, solecism refers to error or improper usage of a language.

Crystal (1999) describes errors as “unacceptable forms produced by someone learning a language, especially a foreign language” (p.108). They refer to consistently deviant productions of forms by a second- language user that would have been rendered differently by a competent native speaker of the target language (Olaoye 2008). Therefore, errors are an integral part of second language knowledge that manifest in deviation from or violation of rules and conventions in usage.

In second-language discourse, errors have been distinguished from mistakes. Olaniyi (2016) opines that errors occur when a second language user internalises the wrong grammar of a language, resulting in faulty expressions rooted in the learner’s (user’s) ignorance of the acceptable rules of the language. He says that a language user makes mistakes in a language they are competent in because of such factors as loss of concentration, due to distractions, fatigue, nervousness or fright, and can be self-corrected when their attention is drawn to such inappropriateness.

The causes of solecisms in second language usage are explicit and diverse. Olaniyi (2016), summarises the causes as learner-related, teacher-related, curriculum-related as well as competence and performance related. Alradi (2018) identifies interlingual and intralingual causes, and mentions overgeneralisation, faulty teaching, fossilisation, avoidance and hypercorrection as some intralingual factors. A communication strategy could be a source of error.

Morpho-syntactic Solecisms

Morpho-syntax is an aspect of the levels of linguistic analysis that refers to the internal structure of words and the way words are strung together to form phrases, clauses and sentences. Thus, morpho-syntactic solecisms are grammatical errors involving both morphology (the structure and form of words) and syntax (the arrangement of words and phrases to create well-formed sentences). These solecisms occur when there is a violation of the expected morphological or syntactic rules of the language, especially in how morphemes combine to form grammatical constructions.

Morphological and syntactic solecisms impinge on the writing efficiency of learners and users of the English language. Mastering English is critical to writing well. Cam and Tran (2017) observe that the lack of grammatical knowledge is responsible for students' inefficiency in English. According to Gayo and Widodo (2018), the types of morphological and syntactic errors include omission error, addition error, misformation error and misordering error. More elaborately, Ogonwa and Chiedu (2018) list the following as examples of morpho-syntactic errors: deviant use of verbs, use of contracted forms of words, non-differentiation of countable and mass nouns, misuse of prepositions, ignorance of question tags, omission of articles, deviant use of reflexive pronouns, redundant use of modifiers, redundant use of amplifiers and redundant use of adjectives.

These solecisms depict a marked departure from a native speaker's competence in English, being viewed as "deviance" or "deviation". Instances of departure that are decidedly bad or wrong, having gone against known grammatical traditions, are examples of "deviance", whereas instances that are still manageable and do not impede mutual intelligibility constitute "deviation". From cognitive and psycholinguistic perspectives, Pinker (2015) emphasises that morpho-syntactic solecisms can reflect stages in language acquisition and learning where learners overgeneralise rules, and that these errors are seen as windows into the mental grammar that speakers construct as they internalise language.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored in the core foundation of Error Analysis (EA). Vanpattern and Benati (2010) define Error Analysis as a research tool characterised by a set of principles for identifying, describing and explaining L2 learners' errors. In other words, EA is a technique in applied linguistics used to systematically study errors that second language users make in the course of learning and using their target language. Al-khresheh (2016) states that Stephen Pit Corder first used EA in the "late 1970s", and from that time till now, it became a prevalent approach for describing foreign language errors. Corder (1974) describes a four-stage procedure of EA as the collection stage, identifying stage, describing stage and the explanation stage. Despite its shortcomings, Al-Khresheh (2016) further declares that Error Analysis still plays a fundamental role in investigating, identifying and describing second- language users' errors and their causes. The current researcher agrees wholeheartedly with this position because it aligns with the paper's aim.

Methodology

Given the fact that the study is aimed at gaining contextual and in-depth knowledge about a real-world situation (occurrence of errors in the official communication documents of a specific institution), the case study research design was adopted. Using the purposive sampling technique, thirty (30) documents written between April 2021 and March 2023, i.e. hard copies of memoranda were selected from different offices in the College. The identified solicisms were analysed and accordingly grouped into morpho-syntactic typology of errors, highlighting the dominant type of solecisms, and establishing their frequency, percentage and rank. The paper utilised Padilla and Padilla's (2021) adaptation of Honey's (1998) error categorisation. A mixed-method, qualitative-quantitative approach, was used in the paper. The former was employed to

identify, describe and explain the errors, while the latter was used to account for the frequency and percentage of the errors observed in the memoranda.

Findings and Discussion

The study, in achieving its aim, shows that there are morpho-syntactic solecisms in the internal memoranda issued from the Registry Department of the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. Thirty (30) memoranda were purposively selected and analysed. These thirty (30) memoranda were issued between April 2021 and March 2023, thereby bringing the currency of the problem that motivated the study to the fore.

A total of two hundred and six (206) solecisms were found in the thirty (30) memoranda examined. Findings showed that the memos used in official communication from the Registry Department of the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo were fraught with morpho-syntactic solecisms. These errors, following Padilla and Padilla's (2021) adaptation of Honey's (1998) categorisation, are article, capitalisation, fragment/incomplete sentence, genitive, misinformation/spelling, misordering, pluralisation, punctuation, redundant/collocational/formulaic, subject-verb agreement, tense/aspect and word choice errors.

Table 1: Error categories, description and samples

Error category	Description	Samples
Article	Misuse or omission of the definite article "the" and indefinite articles "a/an".	"Mrs...has been given () temporary appointment..."
Capitalisation	Incorrect use of initial capitalisation in common nouns and omission of	"...for the 2020/2021 <u>a</u> cademic <u>s</u> ession..."

	initial capitalisation in institutional terms, in spite of the fact that they are common nouns.	
Fragment/Incomplete Sentence	Applying a full stop in a set of words that does not give a complete meaning.	“Who has in the past 4 months been given temporary appointment as a Higher Executive Officer in the College”.
Genitive	Wrong use or omission of possessive markers “s/s’” to indicate singular and plural forms, respectively	“Please note that...should be released to students’ upon presentation of the following”
Misformation/spelling	Incorrect couching of word forms, including the use of Americanisms in formal institutional writing	“Skillful”
Misordering	Putting words in the wrong order in an expression	“Registration Course Form”
Pluralisation	Omission or addition of the plural markers in count and uncount nouns respectively	“Machineries”
Punctuation	Addition or omission of full stops, commas, semi colons, colons, hyphen, and	“am” (in time expression)

	slash in expressions	
Redundant/Collocational/Formulaic	Unnecessary repetition, incorrect collocation and misuse of fixed expressions or idioms	“Please, kindly take necessary action”
Subject-verb agreement	Failure of the verb form of a sentence to agree with its subject in number, person or gender	“The 200 level students identity cards is hereby forwarded...”
Tense-Aspect	Use of the wrong tense form or aspect marker for the intended time or meaning	“...that some Heads of Departments are recommending staff...this a times affected their primary assignments...that would be created...”
Word choice	Inappropriate selection of words in given contexts	“...to your successor in officer before proceeding to your new office”

Table 1 above shows the twelve (12) error categories, their description and samples of errors. An article error is shown in the omission of an indefinite article “a” before “...temporary appointment...” in the sample. As regards capitalisation error, the words “academic session” in the sample, though common nouns are supposed to have initial capitalisation because “...the 2020/2021 academic session” is an institutional term requiring initial capitalisation in formal institutional writing. In relation to a fragment/incomplete sentence, the sample “...who has in the past 4 months been given temporary appointment as a Higher Executive Officer in the College.”

is a dependent clause that is not supposed to end in a full stop but a comma. Genitive error type is observed in “students” (a contextually wrong inclusion of a possessive marker) as shown in the sample. An example of misformation/spelling error is “skillful”, American English form of the British form “skilful”. Misordering error is observed in “Registration Course Form” instead of “Course Registration Form” as observed in the data.

The word “machineries” as shown in the sample is a wrongly pluralised uncount noun, “machinery”, indicating a pluralisation error. There are redundant/collectional/formulaic errors in the data. In Table 1, the use of “please” and “kindly” together might be considered tautological in formal institutional writing. The subject-verb agreement error as shown in the sample indicates that the use of the singular verb “is” does not agree with the plural subject “The 200 level students Identity cards...” Apropos of tense-aspect error, the sample shows the use of a present progressive tense “recommending” with a simple past tense “affected” and future expression “would be created”, thereby making the sentence awkward. The use of the word “officer” in the sample instead of “office” is a word choice error.

Table 11: Error Categories, Frequency, Percentage and Ranking

Error Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
Article	31	15.0%	2 nd
Capitalisation	21	10.2%	5 th
Fragment/Incomplete Sentence	1	05.%	11 th
Genitive	13	6.3%	7 th
Misformation/Spelling	17	8.3%	6 th
Miordering	3	1.5%	10 th
Pluralisation	6	2.9%	9 th
Punctuation	53	25.7%	1 st

Redundant/Collectional/Formuliac	26	12.6%	3 rd
Subject-verb agreement	7	3.4%	8 th
Tense/Aspect	6	2.9%	9 th
Word Choice	22	10.7%	4 th
Total	206	100%	

Table II above shows the error categories, frequencies, percentages and rankings of the errors.

Findings show that the punctuation category, with 53 cases (25.9%), ranks first in the frequency of errors observed in the memoranda produced at the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. This finding is in corroboration with earlier parallel findings of the dominance of punctuation errors (Darus and Subramaniam, 2009, Adekeye and Adesina, 2019). The article error category with 31 cases (15%) ranks second in the study. With 26 cases (12.6%), the redundant/collocational/formulaic error category takes the third position in the ranking order, while word choice error category with 22 (10.7%) occupies the fourth position.

Capitalisation error category ranks fifth with 21 cases (10.2%), and the misformation/spelling category, having 17 examples (8.3%) takes the sixth position in terms of the number of errors committed in the data. Genitive error typology with 13 cases (6.3%) is the seventh while subject-verb agreement category takes the eighth position. Pluralisation and tense/aspect error types with 6 cases each share the ninth position in the ranking order. With 3 (1.5%) and 1(0.5%) case(s) each, misordering and fragment/incomplete sentence error categories appear in the penultimate and lowest rung of the ranking order, respectively.s

Conclusion

The study found that morpho-syntactic solecisms were prevalent in the memoranda produced by the Registry Department of the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. Findings show twelve (12) error categories, namely article, capitalisation, fragment/incomplete sentence,

genitive, misformation/spelling, misordering, pluraisation, punctuation, redundant/collectional/formulaic, subject-verb agreement, tense/aspect and word choice. Findings also established that punctuation with 53 cases (25.7%) was the most frequently committed error typology, whereas the fragment/collocational/formulaic category, with only one case (0.5%), ranked at the bottom in both frequency and percentage of the errors observed in the study.

Furthermore, findings revealed that the sources of the solecisms were both linguistic (interlingual) and developmental (intralingual), indicating language transfer and inadequate mastery of the English Language. Therefore, the paper recommended that writers of memoranda in the Registry Department of the institution in question should engage in personal developmental efforts to improve their written English skills. In addition, the authorities of the institution should prioritise staff training and retraining on the know-how of formal institutional writing.

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